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Improving First-Year Engineering Students' Spatial Reasoning through Interactive Animation Training and Virtual Objects

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INTRODUCTION

Spatial reasoning research has a long history in various fields including engineering, design, geology, chemistry, dentistry and medicine. Spatial reasoning refers to being able to mentally represent and manipulate visual-spatial information. Spatial reasoning involves several subskills – visualization, spatial relation, mental rotation, and mental cutting [1]. Mental cutting enables someone to imagine the interior of an object; mental rotation enables one to envision how an object appears in different positions (views); spatial relation enables one to understand how objects relate to each other in space.

Even though similar processes are involved in each of the subskills, researchers encourage looking at each of them separately [2].

Spatial reasoning ability has been linked to success in STEM disciplines, specifically in relation to mathematics conceptualization, design thinking, graphical representation and problem solving. There is a vast amount of research regarding individual and gender differences in spatial ability. For the last decade, spatial visualization training has been offered to freshman engineering students, as many incoming engineering students need development and enhancement of spatial reasoning. Difficulty recognizing cross sections of three-dimensional structures can place individuals with low spatial ability at a learning disadvantage in engineering, and particularly engineering design.

In the current study we designed an intervention with the aim to improve participants' mental cutting subskills as the ability to recognize and mentally manipulate the cross-sectional structure of materials and mechanisms is a fundamental skill in engineering [3]. In this experimental study, we investigated the efficacy of a brief training protocol which used interactive animation and virtual objects to train low spatial ability participants to recognize the two-dimensional shapes of primitive three-dimensional geometric solids. We also investigated transfer of learning from the trained geometric figures to novel stimuli. One goal of this study was to replicate the results of a previous experiment with a different population (engineering students vs. liberal arts students).

1 RELATED WORK

1.1 Spatial ability training

Several meta-analysis studies suggest that spatial reasoning can be developed and enhanced through training [4, 5]. Various contributors in engineering graphics research have used numerous approaches to develop spatial visualization skills [6]. Scholars claim that even short instruction can substitute for 3 years of untutored development in spatial visualization [7]. One of the major initiatives in spatial skills, led by Sorby and Wysocki, was the development and implementation of a structured training program, situated within the first-year engineering curricula, for undergraduate engineering students with identified low spatial skills [8]. Regardless of all the efforts done in this area, educators are still looking for best practices for developing spatial reasoning skills and for instructional methods and educational tools that lead to performance gain and transfer.

1.2 Physical and virtual objects

Studies have shown that manipulation of physical objects can improve performance gains and transfer in the context of spatial visualization training [9, 10]. The Enhancing Visualization Skills-Improving Options and Success (EnVISION) project was introduced in 2007 to test and enhance the spatial visualization skills of incoming engineering students. The EnVISION curriculum incorporates booklet exercise materials in a traditional classroom environment and its approach was initially used by seven U. S. universities, including our institution. The EnVISION course is targeted to students who have been identified as needing remedial instruction in spatial visualization. Materials developed for the project include a student workbook, software and teacher's resource guide, quizzes and lecture materials (power point slides). Snap blocks, physical cubes that can be snapped together, were used to create models of

the objects students are asked to sketch. Foam hexagonal prisms with longitudinal hole (pool noodles), cut along several different axes, were also used at our institution as a class aid to help students see how an object's features may appear elongated, shortened, or unaltered on the section created by the cutting plane.

In addition to physical objects, scholars have been using virtual models to effectively represent three-dimensional structures in spatial reasoning training [11]. The software developed for the EnVISION program incorporated virtual geometric objects that could be rotated and sliced, and was shown to be successful in training spatial visualization in a semester-long course.

1.3 Animation as a tool for spatial training

Animation, in which an object is presented in a series of static images each slightly changed from the previous, can be used to depict spatial transformation. The dynamic nature of animation correlates well with the dynamic cognitive processes found by cognitive scientists to occur in visuospatial working memory when one envisions a spatial transformation. However the speed of the animation can make it challenging to isolate individual images in ways that allow one to incorporate the result in their long term memory and thus learning. Providing opportunity for the learner to control the speed and direction of the animation through an interactive interface may help. The ability to pause an animation within an interactive interface also provides for the opportunity to have the learner perform a complementary learning activity, such as drawing.

2 METHODOLOGY

This work is collaborative, bridging cognitive psychology, engineering education and engineering design graphics. We are motivated by evidence of the malleability of spatial thinking and by a need to develop new methods to train spatial thinking skills. In this study, we utilized an intervention that we previously developed and tested with science students, to develop mental cutting (or cross-sectional) skills of first-year engineering students with low spatial skills. The stimuli in our experiment are derived from simple geometric solids (cone, cube, cylinder, prism and pyramid), which are among the most elementary recognizable three-dimensional forms. We hypothesized that effective training for this task would permit participants to recognize and visualize the shapes of two-dimensional cross sections of geometric solids.

2.1 Training protocol using virtual models and interactive animation

In this proof-of-concept study the intervention used interactive animation, integrated with drawing and feedback, to train first-year engineering students to identify the two-dimensional cross sections of three-dimensional objects. The participants in the study were first shown a simple geometric figure and a cutting plane to be used to slice the object and were asked to draw the resulting cross section. Next, participants checked the accuracy of their drawings by advancing an interactive cutting plane through a virtual three-dimensional solid that represented the object shown in the drawing trial. As the participant advanced the cutting plane, the correct cross-sectional shape of the drawing trial was revealed and the participant copied the correct shape adjacent to

their drawing. We hypothesized that visual feedback provided by observing the correct cross-sectional shape would improve performance. We predicted that participants who received the intervention would significantly outperform a control group on visualizing cross section for the test figures they viewed during training. We also hypothesized that this result would transfer to new figures they had not trained on.

Participants were assigned to an experimental (N=18) and a control (N=18) group. In the experimental group, participants spent approximately 10-15 minutes with minimal feedback from an experimenter interacting with the virtual objects. Participants in the control group spent the same amount of time playing Tetris.

All participants had completed a cross-section solid test – The Santa Barbara Solid Test (SBST) and some demographics questions before the manipulation. After completing the training or playing Tetris, students from both groups completed the same cross-section solid test and a new Crystallographic Forms Test (the Crystal cross-section test).

Table 1. Training Condition

Experimental condition	Control condition
<p>4 interactive animations Train two versions of object consecutively (e.g., ortho cone, followed by oblique cone)</p> <p>Object 1: orthogonal cone Object 2: oblique cone Object 3: orthogonal cube Object 4: oblique cube</p>	<p>Access to Tetris game (online game)</p> <p>This game aims to create order out of chaos and to provide intellectual sport with mental stimulation. The game requires players to strategically rotate, move, and drop a procession of Tetriminos that fall into the rectangular matrix at increasing speeds.</p>
<p>4 drawing trials (color images of Objects 1-4, printed on 8 x 11 paper)</p>	
Sharp pencils with erasers	Sharp pencils with erasers
Drawing Packets	Tetris game competition score sheet

Participants: Participants were 36 undergraduate engineering students (M=14; F=22) who met a criterion for low spatial ability (rotation test score of 18 or less) and who were enrolled in an introduction to spatial visualization course at a large public university. Participants were assigned to an intervention group (7 males and 11 females) and a control group (7 males and 11 females). A Mann-Whitney U test showed no significant difference between the mean pre-test scores of the intervention (M = .35, SD = .12) and the control (M=.38, SD = .17) group.

Performance and transfer measures: The SBST [12] was used for both the pre- and post-training performance assessment. This test involves identifying the resulting cross-section when a solid object is cut with a cutting plane. The object in each test question is created from four fundamental objects (cone, cube, cylinder, prism and pyramid), where the object could be fundamental object itself; a compound object involving two of the fundamental shapes positioned relative to each other but

intersecting only at a surface; or an embedded object in which one of the objects is totally embedded within the other. In each test question the object is intersected by a cutting plane. For half of the questions the cutting plane is orthogonal to the object's primary axis (either horizontal or vertical); for the other half the cutting plane is oblique, positioned at a non-orthogonal angle to the primary axis of the object. Each question presents four possible resulting cross-sections from which to choose. As reported by the test developer, "Cronbach's Alpha computed across all items is .91 and for the major subscales of the test is: simple figures, $\alpha=.79$; joined figures, $\alpha=.80$; embedded figures, $\alpha=.73$; orthogonal figures, $\alpha=.84$; and oblique figures, $\alpha=.85$ " [12]. An example of the SBST is given in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. An example of Santa Barbara Solid Test (SBST)

Following treatment and completion of the post-test, study participants also completed the Crystal Test [13], to measure the transferability of the learned cross-sectional skill to objects different from those used in the training. The objects in the Crystal Test are based on idealized crystalline shapes with a cutting plane. Like the SBST, the cutting plane may be orthogonal to the primary axes of the crystal structure or oblique to the primary axes. Figure 2 is an example of one of the 15 multiple choice questions. Each of the objects is symmetric front to back and shading is used to indicate depth. Three mutually perpendicular axes are shown for reference. The test has been used to assess spatial thinking skills that are required in mineralogy, structural geology and other geology courses.

Interactive training animation: Participants in the experimental group were asked to work through a series of four interactive animations. In the interactive animation an image of one of the fundamental shapes (cone, cube, cylinder, prism and pyramid) was displayed and a cutting plane is advanced through the object. As the cutting plane advances an image of the resulting instantaneous cross-section is displayed to the side of the object. The speed and direction of the advancement of the cutting plane is controlled by the participant using a computer mouse, allowing the participant to explore the development of the two-dimensional cross-section at a self-determined

pace. Participant were asked to sketch the expected cross-section and compare it to the actual cross-section as they advance the cutting plane.

Fig. 2. A sample problem from the Crystallographic Forms Test

3 RESULTS

3.1 Performance on cross-section solid test trained, similar, and new figures

The 30 SBST test questions were classified into three categories (trained, similar, and new) for analysis of training and transfer. Four trained figures were orthogonal and oblique sections of the cone and the cube, identical to those used in the interactive animations. Similar figures were composed of two solids, at least one of which had been trained during the intervention. New figures were composed of two untrained solids.

Figure 3 shows pre-and post-test performance means and standard errors by object and condition. Given the unequal sample sizes by sex and a non-normal distribution of mean scores in the control condition, we used the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test to assess group differences across the three categories of objects. At pre-test, there were no significant differences between the intervention and control groups for trained figures, similar figures or new figures (all p -values $>.30$). In contrast, participants who completed the animation training significantly outperformed the control at post-test on trained figures, $p<.004$, and on new figures, $p<.05$. There were no significant differences between the trained and control groups on similar figures.

Fig. 3. Pre-and post-test performance means on SBST

There was a significant difference by sex in the pre-test scores of the experimental group. Males in this group had a mean score of .17, while females had a more reasonable score of .44. One plausible alternative explanation is that male participants did not put real effort into taking the pre-test.

3.2 Performance on transfer objects

Four of the 15 items on the Crystals test were selected to be used to measure transferability of the training to new objects. No significant difference in the scores on these four problems were observed for the two groups. One plausible explanation for the lack of significant difference can be that the objects in the four problems were considered very easy and too intuitive.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

While replicating previous studies, this experiment demonstrates the utility of using animation training and virtual objects in an introductory engineering class. In summary, our study findings reveal the following: First, there was a significant effect of the experimental condition on trained problems, with participants in the trained condition outperforming the control group. Second, we found a significant effect of the experimental condition on the new problems, with the trained condition again outperforming the control. Thirdly, there were significant differences between the two groups at pre-test, and no significant differences between groups at post-test.

While the small sample size is a recognized limitation, this proof-of-concept study demonstrates that the use of interactive animation training may add to the development and enhancement of spatial reasoning for students with recognized low spatial skills. Our next steps in this area of research include replicating the study results with a larger sample of the same population with equal numbers of male and female participants. We will consider offering an incentive appropriate for the experiment design to address the concern that some participants did not put serious effort into completing the pre-test. We will also use the results of the entire Crystals Test for measuring the ability to transfer learning from the training to new experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mishkin, M.; Ungerleider, L.G.; Macko, K.A. Object vision and spatial vision: Two cortical pathways. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 6, (1983) 414--417.
- [2] Oman, C.; Shebilske, W.L.; Richards, J.T.; Tubré, T., C.; Beall, A., C.; Natapoff, A. Three Dimensional Spatial Memory and Learning in Real and Virtual Environments. *Spatial Cognition and Computation*, 2, (2002) 355-372.
- [3] Sorby, S. (2009). Educational research in developing 3D spatial skills for engineering students. *International Journal of Science Education*, 31(3), 459–480.
- [4] Baenninger, M., & Newcombe, N. (1989). The role of experience in spatial test performance: A meta-analysis. *Sex Roles*, 20(5–6), 327–344.
- [5] Uttal, D. H.,Meadow, N. G., Tipton, E., Hand, L. L., Alden, A. R.,Warren, C., et al. (2013). The malleability of spatial skills: A meta-analysis of training studies. *Psychological Bulletin*, 139, 352–402.
- [6] Mohler, J. L., and Miller, C. L. (2009). Improving spatial ability with mentored sketching. *Engineering Design Graphics Journal*, 72.1.
- [7] Rovet, J. (1983). *The education of spatial transformations*. In D. R. Olson (Ed.), *Spatial cognition: The structure and development of mental representations of spatial relations* (pp. 164-181). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [8] Sorby, S. A., and Wysock, A. F. (2003). *Introduction to 3D Spatial Visualization: an active approach*. Cengage Learning.
- [9] Brinkmann, E. (1996). Programmed Instruction as a technique for improving spatial visualization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 50(2):179-84.
- [10] Lord, T. (1985). Enhancing visuo-spatial aptitude of students. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 22(5):395 – 405.
- [11] Duesbury, RT. (1996). Effect of practice in a computer-aided design environment in visualizing three-dimensional objects from two-dimensional orthographic projections. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81(3):249-260.
- [12] Cohen, C.A. & Hegarty, M. (2012). Inferring cross sections of 3D objects: A new spatial thinking test. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 22(6), 868-874.
- [13] Ormand, C. J., Shipley, T. F. & Tikoff, B. (2016). Ten Years of SILC Research on Spatial Thinking and Learning in Geoscience: What We've Learned and Produced: Geological Society of America annual meeting (Denver, CO).